

Paper 1

**A STUDY ON SOCIAL SKILLS AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS
AMONG D.EL.ED (Diploma in Elementary Education) TRAINEES OF
DISTRICT INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING KASARGOD**

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ABSTRACT

The destiny of the country is being shaped in the classrooms. The teacher has an important role to play for national development and social change. The first and foremost responsibility of the teacher is towards the welfare of the society and his students in particular. The teacher has to treat each individual as an end in himself and to give him the opportunity to develop his skills and abilities and potentialities to the full. The present study is concerned with Social skills and academic achievements of the D El.Ed trainees .Social skills, as the components of behaviour, allow us to interact with others and maintain healthy relationships in the society. Although the concept of social skills is not very new, many scholars have just started to realize their importance in life and have begun to study their role in different aspects of life of an individual. This paper presents an overview of the importance of social skills in academic achievement and in every stage of life of teachers as well as students. Social skills are very necessary for good professional life. Strong social skills help in facilitating interpersonal interactions which lead to efficient job outcomes. As a teacher D El Ed training moulds them to be a good teacher in the society they have to interact with students, parents, doctors, etc.so this study is very relevant. Teachers have an important role to renew the curriculum in this emerging society .From the study it is found that there is a positive relationship between social skills and academic achievements.

Key Words: Social Skills, Academic Achievement, Success El ED Trainees.

Introduction

The present study titled “A study on social skills and academic achievements among D El.Ed trainees of District Institute of Education and training (DIET) Kasaragod. Social skills are synonyms with the term Life Skills, Soft Skills. A relatively new concept social skills with its significance has emerged in the educational and social scenario. Social skills are highly valued in people in the society.

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The term academic achievement stands for the identifiable operations that teacher trainees are expected to perform on the curriculum materials prescribed for a course. This term has a wide connotation. It does not indicate the marks alone secured by the teacher in the totality of the academic gains acquired within the training institution.

Need and significance of the study

In this competitive world it is highly essential to see that each individual is equipped with the right skills that would enable him to meet the challenges of the present day. It has to take special care that no students of the society is left behind. Good social skills critical to successful functioning in life .Children pickup positive social skills through their everyday interactions with adults and peers .The type of instructions that the students receive can also influence their social skills to a large extend .Hence fourth it is important that the teacher trainees should recognise when and where children pickup behaviour that might be determinant to their development or safeties. Training period of teacher is considered to be the most critical period to their profession, it is therefore very essential that suitable environment be provided to the teacher trainees wherein they can express their talents freely without any inhibitions.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To study the academic achievements among the D El Ed trainees of Kasargod district
- 2) To study the social skills among the D El Ed trainees of Kasargod district
- 3) To study whether there exist any significant difference between the social skills among the male and female D.El.Ed trainees of Kasargod district
- 4) The study whether there exist any significant difference between academic achievement among the male and female D.El.Ed trainees of Kasargod district
- 5) To study whether there exist any significant difference between the social skills among D.El.Ed trainees of rural and urban areas of Kasargod district.
- 6) To study whether there exist any significant difference between the academic achievements among D.El.Ed trainees of rural and urban areas

Related studies on social skills

Under this section studies related to social skills and components of social skills are reported . PhD
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(2010) conducted a study on students' academic achievements and school success behaviour

Mice, Darrell (2009) Study about the strategies for promoting social development .The findings of the study suggested that positive verbal environments enhance children's positive sense of self and provide safe supporting contacts to develop and practice social skills

Chandrasekhar (2007) found that planned systematic training programs help the student in developing their soft skills which may assist them to make worthy of moving ahead in this competitive era. The effects on student's emotional and behavioural difficulties of teacher student interactions, student's social skills and classroom context. –

Maria Poulow (2014) Children's emotional and behavioural difficulties are the result of multiple individual, social and contextual factors working in concert. The current paper proposes a theoretical framework for interpreting student's emotional and behavioural difficulties in classrooms, by taking into consideration teacher-student interactions, students' social skills and classroom context. Based on Bronfenbrenner's model, according to which process, person and context are the main sources of children's development, the current paper combines three theoretical approaches : Firstly, in terms of process, the system communication approach, which refers to teacher-student interactions; secondly, in terms of person, social and emotional learning, which refers - 44 - to children's social skills; and thirdly, in terms of classroom context, the achievement goal theory, with its emphasis on the mastery of classroom goal structure.

Related studies on academic achievements

Sexton Jami (2010) conducted an action research on "Increasing student achievement through data-driven ability grouping and instructional practices" darshan of the study suggests a positive relationship between detailed item analysis and student placements the results also show a positive relationship between using detailed data analysis for instructional planning and increasing student achievements

Morgan, Hani (2010) made a study on "Teaching native American students". Research suggests that traditional classroom and environments often interfere with the way of Native American children learn. The author suggests that, to teach effectively the educator should be aware of cultural and learning differences this understanding is gained and when they are aware of student's differences. Once this understanding is gained and when they are aware of student's differences teachers can introduce task to teach students skills they have likely avoided or failed to acquire

Usha P. & Rekha (2009). “Emotional competence and mental health as predictors of academic achievement”. Kerala and Thrissur. The present study has been designed to investigate the emotional competence and mental

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health as predictors of academic achievement among the secondary school pupils of Kerala. The findings of the study imply that emotional competence is the best predictor of achievement in physics of secondary school pupils. Therefore more emphasis should be laid on infusing emotional literacy into the standard curriculum and to create proper school climate to enhance the development and application of emotional skills among pupils.

Methodology

The present study is a descriptive survey where a survey was undertaken to study the social skills and academic achievements of D.El.Ed trainees of Kasargod district .

Variables of the study

In the present study the variables taken into consideration by the investigator to be studied as follows

Social skills

Social skills are defined as those social interpersonal and task related behaviour that produce positive consequences. In the present study social skills simply goal-directed and well-organized behaviour like interpersonal relationship, communication, friendship and listening at appropriate times and in specific. This was measured by social skills rating scale constructed by the investigator

Components of social skills

- 1 Interpersonal relationship
- 2 Communication
- 3 Concern for others
- 4 Friendship
- 5 Co –operation
- 6 Listening

Academic achievements

Academic achievements refers to the percentage of aggregate marks obtained by the D El Ed trainees in the examinations .The marks were noted from the academic records of the respective training institutes

D.El.Ed Trainees

The D El Ed trainees of Kasargod district refers to the trainings teachers belonging to both sexes between the age group 18 to26 getting above higher secondary education following the Kerala state and

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National syllabus ,situated in urban and rural areas of Kasargod district

Kasargod district

Kasargod district is one of the 14 districts of Kerala state

Tools used for the study

For the purpose of measuring the variables selected for the study the following tools were used bythe investigator

1. **Social skill Rating scale** constructed by the investigator to measure the social skills of the students
2. **Achievement test** prepared by the teacher
3. **Observation schedule constructed by the investigator**

Population and sample of the study

In the present study the population consisted of 160 D.El.Ed trainees of urban and rural areas in Kasargod district. The trainees were of age 18 to 26 years. There were 20 boys and140 girls in the sample. The students in the sample selected through purposive sampling based on gender and locality of the D El Ed trainees.

Statistical Techniques used

To study the social skills and academic achievements of D El Ed. trainees of Kasargod district the following Statistical Techniques were used

Descriptive statistics Mean, Median, Standard deviation and graphical representation namely frequency polygon and Ogives were used inferential statistics Test was employed to study the significant differences between the social skills and academic achievements of D.El.Ed trainees of Kasargod district

Data analysis and interpretation

1. Academic achievement among the DEl.Ed trainees of Kasaragod district is above average
2. The frequency of scores of social skills among the DEl.Ed trainees of Kasaragod district is approximately normally distributed

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3. Social skills among the female DEI.Ed trainees of Kasaragod district is significantly higher than the social skills among the male D El.Ed trainees of Kasargod district

4 Academic achievements among the female D.El.Ed trainees of Kasargod district is higher than the academic achievements among the male D.El.Ed trainees of Kasaragod district

5 D El Ed trainees of urban and rural areas do not differ in their social skills

7 D.El.Ed trainees of urban and rural areas do not differ in their academic achievements.

Major findings

*Male and Female D El Ed trainees of Kasargod district is significantly differ in their social skills

*Social skills among the Female D El Ed trainees of Kasargod district is significantly greater than the social skills among the Male D El Ed trainees of Kasargod district

* Male and Female DEI Ed trainees of Kasaragod district is significantly different in their academic achievements

*Academic achievements of Female D El Ed trainees of Kasargod district is significantly greater than the academic achievement of Male D El Ed trainees of Kasargod district

* D.El.Ed trainees of Urban and rural areas do not differ in the academic achievement

*DEI Ed Trainees of Urban and rural areas do not differ in their social skills

*There is a positive relationship between social skills and academic achievements among the D.El.Ed trainees of Kasargod district

Educational implications

1 Relevant activities need to enhance the social skills of male D El.Ed Trainees

2 Introduce several learning activities to enhance the academic achievements of D. El.Ed trainees of Kasaragod district

3 The study has revealed that there is a positive relationship between social skills and academic achievements. Hence measures need to be introduced to enhance the social skills by organising curricular and non-curricular activities so that academic achievement can be improved.

4 The present study reveals that social skills among D.El.Ed trainees in Kasargod district is

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approximately normally distributed. The findings implies that the trainees could improve their social skills in the classroom situation and outside classroom situation.

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